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Innovative Training Methods and Technologies in Western Vocational Military Education

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***Annotation:** This article explores the integration of modern teaching methods and innovative approaches within military educational institutions, particularly emphasizing practices at the U.S. Army Command and General Staff College in Fort Leavenworth, Kansas. It underscores the significance of interactive teaching methods, such as collaborative learning, problem-based learning, and technology-enhanced instruction, in enhancing the quality of professional military education. The article discusses how these methods contribute to the development of critical thinking skills essential for military leaders in dynamic and complex operational environments.*

Furthermore, the article examines the role of experiential learning, where students engage in real-world scenarios and simulations, fostering a deeper understanding of military strategy and decision-making processes. The seminar methodology, encouraging open dialogue and the exchange of ideas among peers, is highlighted as a vital component in cultivating a culture of continuous learning and professional growth. Overall, the findings suggest that the adoption of modern pedagogical practices in military education not only prepares personnel for current challenges but also equips them with the skills necessary to adapt to future uncertainties.

***Key words:** Modernization, innovation, competition, unprecedented, system, competence, educational process, subjects, ICT, science and technology, integrity, commonality, universality, differentiation.*

In-depth study of integration between modern teaching methods practiced at higher military educational institutions of Western foreign countries, is based on the direct examination of the education and training process during the author's foreign business trip to the U.S. Army Command and Staff College (in the city of Kansas).

The so-called interactive teaching methods have been "ascending" in Western education for several decades. Indeed, they have played a significant role in the educational system of the West over the past

century. In the twenty-first century, popularization of interactive methods across the entire range of educational services, ranging from public schools to universities and from various disciplines, including business, military art and science has become the most striking experience.

To date, educational theorists have moved emphasis towards the so-called empirical learning that nowadays, has become one of the main incentives for interactive teaching methods in the U.S. vocational military education. As it will be shown in the article, this is hardly a recent breakthrough, but the result of natural evolution in education that has been lasting for centuries. The idea that learning from personal experience or by means of active participation is more effective than passive listening has been reaffirmed by strong and durable history.

Redirection of the focus from the teacher to the student has become the second source of modern reformation in Western education. With good reason, the concept of teaching as the transfer of knowledge from an expert to a beginner emphasizes great importance to the experience of the one who lectures or teaches. However, the general paradigm has changed over the twentieth century. At present, the expression "student-oriented" is used regularly in order to focus on the student's thinking.

The third main force behind the new approaches in education is the emphasis on the development of so-called "lifelong" students. In other words, this idea involves enlightenment of people so that they are more capable of learning in the future. Development of critical thinking is one of the key criteria for success in the future. In fact, universities in the United States and Europe have now widely recognized critical thinking as a fundamental educational goal of any higher education. According to this point of view, in the future, those who can think critically will be the ones who are best prepared intellectually for solving problems, promoting their professions and improving society as a whole¹.

In all likelihood, interactive teaching methods were independently discovered and widely used in many cultures even before professional educators began to think theoretically. Indeed, practical value of interactive participation in the teaching and learning process is, to some extent, intuitive. However, this is not taken for granted for everyone, therefore, in many cultures, at different times and in educational contexts, it has lost influence in favor of a more authoritative approach. This authority-based approach, whether in the form of lectures or repeated exercises on the disciple, has become commonplace at all levels of education. Of course, the opinion that a teacher should be an authoritative figure is important in the correct contexts. In fact, in some situations, lectures on fundamental knowledge are extremely effective. However, they rarely cultivate the development of critical and intellectual abilities to the same extent as interactive approaches.

More than ever, the goal of modern educational circles consists in the development of critical thinking skills, which are often best supported by an active dialogue, considering numerous points of view on the problem and an open approach. According to this point of view, it should be incorrectly assumed that the best solution to the problem has already been determined, or that the appeal to the established intellectual authority is a logical action.

Today, modern professional teaching literature, especially about interactive methods or empirical teaching, is so extensive that it often seems that there are no other points of view in this regard. The details of books and articles may vary slightly, but all seem to eventually confirm some aspects of interactive teaching. Seminars for educators on how to use interactive methods are widespread.

¹ Paul, R. (1993). *Critical thinking: what every person needs to survive in a rapidly changing world* (3rd ed.). Rohnert Park, California: Sonoma State University Press.

Therefore, in this study, those works and authors who had the deepest impact on the development of professional military education in the West will be especially noticeable.

In the 80s of the last century, the command staff of the U.S. Army Command and Staff College (hereinafter referred to as the CSC) of the United States Army in Fort Leavenworth, Kansas, led to emphasize experimental training in the area of professional military education. The CSC accepted empirical training as an integral part of its educational philosophy and made sure that all instructors knew how to use it. Nowadays, just as then, all the new CSC instructors must complete the faculty certification course to ensure they are familiar with the teaching philosophy of the college. Gradually, since the 1980s, the CSC has reduced the use of lectures to maximize the amount of training conducted at the seminar level. The number of the seminars' participants, whether at the Command and Staff School or at the School of Advanced Military Studies, is limited to sixteen students in a group. As a rule, seminar leaders pay great attention to post graduate students' participation in discussions. In this case colleges' management is firmly convinced that this is the best environment for training future leaders who can be adaptive, and able to think critically².

Another critical aspect of the CSC approach was to organize seminars in such a way that each seminar participant had a wide range of officer experience based on industry and service affiliation. For example, a typical group must necessarily have one naval service officer (U.S. Navy, U.S. Marines or U.S. Coast Guard), one of the Air Force and one of the five or more Army arms. In addition, each study group will include one, and often two students from foreign countries. Some groups may have a representative from the civil government agencies such as the State Department or the Ministry of Justice. Such an approach significantly reduces the risk of so-called "group thinking" - such a state in which post graduate students quickly begin to think about the same issue of specific problems and minimize discussion. Naturally, as in all the groups of any kind, seminar leaders appear on time, and the most respected teachers are those who know how to encourage/stimulate the contributions of all the discussion group members. The main goal of such an approach is to create an environment in which critical thinking "is flourishing" (is developing).

Instructors (teachers) at the CSC should be flexible enough to switch between open discussions, on the one hand, and directed discussion, on the other. The Advanced Course in the CSC emphasizes that teachers should contribute to the creation of an atmosphere of joint participation in which all participants of the seminar play their role and express their opinion. For example, when discussing tactical or operational problems, such as in Ukraine or Syria, students themselves will often be experts based on their direct experience, at least at some stage of these missions. The best discussions during the lesson will use the experience of students to teach a group in a joint team. In such cases, the instructor can play the role of a moderator.

On the other hand, in subject areas where the majority of students will have insufficient knowledge to conduct a discussion without assistance, the instructor will be more active during the discussion and often provide additional information. In exceptional cases, a short (5–15minutes) lecture may be needed to help the students understand the topic. Often the instructor's comments will be the result of the students' questions. As adult learners, CSC students are happy to learn from each other, but they also want to consult a teacher whose experience exceeds their own. In general, of course, the instructor is responsible for the management of the study group. He is the one who ensures deep discussion and mastering of all the seminar educational objectives and tasks.

² Clausewitz, Carl von. 1984 *On War*. Michael Howard and Peter Paret, trans. ed. Princeton: Princeton University Press, (Book 3, Chapter 1)149.

Each course in the CSC is carefully developed. Educational objectives for each course and study group are designed to reconcile with the comprehensive training goals set by the college. The authors of the curriculum and courses choose compulsory, as well as additional reading materials and offer practical scenarios to stimulate discussions. During the lesson, every teacher has ample opportunities to determine the best way to achieve the goals of the lesson. In some cases, the instructor recommends additional reading literature or forms small subgroups to stimulate learning experience. If the experiment is successful, he may recommend his approach to other instructors. In other words, instructors in the CSC begin with a carefully thought-out plan of the lesson, but can adapt it flexibly according to the developing lesson discussion.

Amid the methodologies that use this flexibility one can come across the so-called "Case Study" methodology. The method of "Case Study" has long been used in various Western universities. However, probably it is most widely associated with the Harvard University School of Business. It was really true, that ten years ago, experts from the CSC faculty of development invited to Kansas the Harvard University experts to give a series of presentations on the best ways on development and use of the "Case Study" methodology. Although, at first glance, such a type of cooperation between business teachers and military teachers may seem surprising, it is worth remembering that in his classic work "On War" Karl von Clausewitz made a direct comparison between these two areas of study. In particular, he noted that any existing chance or reason play an important role in both war and business, for the reason that they are both intercompetative. And here, the logical conclusion is that both areas require the same decision-making processes and that the involved in each area leaders are subject to similar difficulties.

Comprehensive exams taken by the college trainees is another important part of the students' performance assessment. At the School of Command and General Staff, each post graduate student sits a comprehensive exam related to the so-called "general core of education and training", which is normally held from August to December. All post graduate students of the Command and Staff College wishing to obtain a Master's of Military and Science Degree (MSc) must complete an additional oral exam and successfully defend a dissertation paper at the end of the academic year. All students of the Advanced Military Studies School (also a part of the CSC) must also do an oral comprehensive exam at the end of the academic year as a part of their Master's degree (MA).

Since the legislation signed by President Nixon in 1974, the CSC has been nominated to give Master's degree to qualified officers. Since that period of time, the CGSC has become the first Army school or college to confer Master's degree on its graduates. One of the conditions for obtaining such a right was that the CSC entirely complied with the State standards established by accredited academic institutions.

Critical thinking has become a central link in the world of higher education in the United States and Europe as a whole. Similarly, by now, critical thinking has become the cornerstone of education in the entire Army educational system from the top to the bottom. Consequently, throughout their academic progression, Army officers will be aware of such an important skill for a commander as critical thinking. In parallel, all instructors throughout the educational system of the Army undergo the same basic course for teachers so that they can train students within the framework of the unified educational process.

Innovation and conduct of experiments in educational process are also a cardinal feature of teaching and research in the CSC. Over the past decade, the Command and Staff College has formed targeted

research groups manned by officers with experience and interest related to a specific issue presenting interest in the Army.

However, it is well known that the requirement to have a highly qualified faculty is one of the key elements of graduate level education. Since 2003, in accordance with the expectations of the Higher Education Commission, the CSC has been making concerted efforts to develop and master its faculty professional skills. According to the recommendations of the Commission, instructors teaching the Master's Leverage program must have a DSc or PhD degree, although some exceptions may be made in special professions, such as the military, in which long career experience can sometimes compensate for the lack of a scientific degree.

Meanwhile, from the point of view of the theory of education, differences in opinion regarding both approaches and qualifications still remain. It must be borne in mind that despite the fact that it was engulfed in the Army, the concept of discussion education, presented by David Kolb, and individual training styles is still the subject of wide and controversial debates³. For instance, Rejo Miettinen, Finnish educational researcher, asserts that “at present, adult education risks to remain alive as a quasi-scientific academic sphere, but it still does not have any proved grounds or connections with the area of philosophical, anthropological, sociological and psychological researches on teaching and thinking. Moreover, the belief in the mental ability of a person and his individual experience leads us from the analysis of the cultural and social conditions of teaching which are in demand for any serious enterprise that contributes to changes in education and training in real life⁴. In other words, Miettinen is convinced that cultural context plays an important role in education, but this conclusion is not taken into account in David Kolb's theory.

Unfortunately, in most educational and training theories insufficient attention is paid either to the core educational subject or to the professional skills of a teacher. Moreover, in the vital field of cognitive neuroscience, they often pay only lip service by words of mouth in the vital field of cognitive neuroscience. The fact is that almost all researches on teaching and other cognitive processes carried out by education theorists are not confirmed by neuroscience studies. The impact of this deficit is probably incompatible. The concept of experimental teaching, as well as the theory of reflexive thinking and action proposed by John Dewey are likely to remain relevant in all theories or, for that matter, in all subject disciplines. Accordingly, some widespread beliefs about teaching will almost certainly be confirmed by future researches on neurobiology. For example, the ability to perceive experience is so constant and universal that one can hardly doubt that experience is a great incentive to learn. On the other hand, theories, ranging from Bloom's taxonomy, teaching styles, up to the students' self-education abilities in groups, are much more prone to debate. Each of them will likely change significantly as neurophysiological research progresses in the nearest future⁵.

In general, vocational military education in the United States, as well as in Europe, is doing its best to keep up with the “best teaching practices” used in civilian colleges and universities. In fact, as the CSC more actively cooperates with the Higher Education Commission, the CSC sends its own faculty members to participate and give presentations at civil universities during their annual scientific-

³ Kolb, David. 1984. *Experiential Learning: Experience as a source of learning and development*: Englewood Cliffs, NJ: Prentice Hall.

⁴ Miettinen, Reijo. 2000. The Concept of Experiential Learning and John Dewey's Theory of Reflective Thought and Action, « Концепция эмпирического обучения и теория рефлексивных мыслей и действий Джона Дьюи », *The International Journal of Life Long Education*, 19: 1, 54-72.

⁵ Kagan, S. 2005. *Rethinking Thinking – Does Bloom's Taxonomy Align with Brain Science?* **Kagan Online Magazine** San Clemente, CA: Kagan Publishing., Fall www.KaganOnline.com (accessed 25 April 2024).

research conferences and meetings on the regular basis. Since mutual cooperation of the CSC with neighboring civil universities continues to expand, the benefits for both sides are obvious. Indeed, the value of cooperation with civilian academicians is generally considered to be increasingly important, as the U.S. Army normally plans the future of its educational programs and syllabuses jointly with the Higher Education Commission institutions.

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